

PCDD/F, PCB, PBDE AND PAH IN DIGESTATES FROM THREE BIOGAS PLANTS IN FINLAND

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Introduction

Biogas technology is a competitive process for managing biodegradable wastes and by-products. End products from biogas plants can be used as fertilizers or soil improvers, which is of prior importance in recycling depleting nutrients, such as phosphorous. There are approximately 143,000 chemicals registered in the EU. Many of these chemicals are used in households and industry, and they may end up in municipal waste water treatment plants (MWTP). Also manure, industrial by-products and municipal bio waste may contain harmful chemicals. These biological products can be used as raw material in biogas plants (BGP). When BGP end products are used as fertilisers, harmful compounds may accumulate into soil and in the food chain.

Materials and methods

We sampled digestates immediately after biogas reactor from three BGPs during 2010. The plant A uses only MWTP sludge as raw material whereas the plant B processes pig manure and biodegradable industrial by products and sludges. The plant C processes MWTP and industrial sludge and source-sorted and separately collected organic fraction of municipal solid waste. The plant A utilises a prereactor for heating the incoming material ($t = 160\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 30 min, 5–6 bar) prior to the biogas process. In the plant B, the incoming material is heated to $70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ 1 h before biogas reactor. In the plant C, the hygienisation is managed with thermal drying ($t = 95\text{--}104\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, approx. 2 h) of mechanically separated solid fraction after the biogas process. All plants use mesophilic processes with temperatures of $41\text{ to }42\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (plant A), $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (plant B) and $35\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (plant C). Dry matter content of digestates ranged from 5.9 to 9.3%.

Freeze-dried samples were analysed for polychlorinated dibenzo-p-dioxins (PCDD/F), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB), polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDE) and polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH). Analyses of PCDD/F and PCB were performed with HRGC/MS. PCDD/F were analysed according to US EPA 1613 and 8290 or VDI 3499 Part 1. PCBs were analysed according to EN DIN ISO 10382. Analyses of PBDE and PAH were performed with GC-MS-apparatus, PBDEs according to ISO 22032 and PAH according to LUA-NRW, Merkblatt 1. For PCDD/F toxic equivalents (TEQ) were calculated with a set of toxic equivalency factors (TEF) recommended by WHO in 2006¹.

Results and discussion:

PCDD/F and PCB

Lower bound TEQ-concentrations of PCDD/F were highest in the plant A samples that received only MWTP sludges (from $1.5\text{ to }2.0\text{ ng WHO-TEQ kg}^{-1}\text{ d.w.}$) (Figure 1). In the plant C, the TEQ-concentration of PCDD/F ranged from $0.6\text{ to }0.7\text{ ng WHO-TEQ kg}^{-1}\text{ d.w.}$ The lowest TEQ-concentrations of PCDD/F were detected in plant B samples ($\leq 0.003\text{ ng WHO-TEQ kg}^{-1}\text{ d.w.}$). Congener profiles of the PCDD/F in our samples (Figure 2) were similar to the average deposition profile of PCDD/F in Finland between 1997 and 2004 with OCDD as the most abundant congener². Concentrations of PCB were below limit of quantification (LOQ) in all our samples.

PBDE

Lower bound sum concentrations of PBDE were highest in sludge that originated from biogas plant A that received only MWTP sludge (from $280\text{ to }690\text{ }\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}\text{ d.w.}$) (Figure 3). In plant C samples, the concentration of PBDE ranged from $28\text{ to }250\text{ }\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}\text{ d.w.}$ Concentrations of PBDE were below LOQ ($4\text{ to }100\text{ }\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}\text{ d.w.}$) in both samples of the plant B that received animal manure and industrial by products.

The most common PBDE-congeners were deca-BDE and octa-BDE, whereas lower brominated congeners played a minor role. However, deca-BDE was absent in two of our samples. Deca-, octa- and nona-BDEs have been detected in biogas plant end products³. Octa- and nona brominated BDEs may be impurities of the commercial deca-BDE-preparation⁴ or they may also be anaerobic degradation products of the deca-BDE⁵. Penta- and octa brominated BDEs are banned in the EU and use of them is restricted by the Stockholm Convention. They were still present in our samples.

PAH

Lower bound sum concentrations of 16 PAH in BGP end products were highest in the plant A (from 1.2 to 1.8 mg kg⁻¹ d.w.). Sum concentrations of PAH in plant C sludges ranged from 1.0 to 1.1 mg kg⁻¹ d.w. In contrast to PBDE, PAH-compounds were not absent in plant B, where the sum concentration of PAH ranged from 0.06 to 0.80 mg kg⁻¹ d.w. Naphthalene, phenanthrene and pyrene were the most abundant PAHs in our samples.

Figure 1. Lower bound WHO-TEQ-concentrations of PCDD/F in biogas end products from three biogas plants.

Conclusions

Our results show that PCDD/F, PBDE and PAH were present in biogas end products. Concentrations of PCDD/F and PBDE were highest in samples from the plant that received only MWTP sludge, and they were almost absent in samples from the plant that received only animal manure and industrial by-products. PBDE originates likely from industrial and domestic use of these compounds. PAH- and PCDD/F-compounds are formed in incineration processes and they likely originate from the global fallout. PCDD/F congener profile in our samples was similar to the deposition profile in Finland². One reason for low concentration of PCB in our samples may be that PCBs are degraded in anaerobic biogas reactors⁶. We detected also compounds that are globally banned such as penta and octa-BDE.

The large differences in concentrations of the studied compounds in our samples are likely due to differences in input materials of the biogas plants.

Figure 2. Lower bound concentrations and congener profiles of PCDD/F in biogas end products from three biogas plants (lower bound).

Figure 3. Lower bound concentrations and congener profiles of PBDE in biogas end products from three biogas plants.

Figure 4. Lower bound concentrations and compound profiles of PAH-compounds in biogas end products from three biogas plants. Concentrations of other measured PAHs (acenaphthene, acenaphthylene, benzo[ghi]perylene, benzo[k]fluoranthene, dibenzo[a,h]anthracene, indeno [1,2,3-cd] pyrene) were below LOQ (0.05 to 0.75 mg kg⁻¹ d.w.).

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